

**USING MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING AND LEARNING
ENGLISH**

English teachers of the 40th school of
Shavat district, Khorezm region

Ro'zmetova Hulkar

Madrahimova Surayyo

Annotation: This article is written about the appropriate use of modern technologies in learning and teaching English, and the teacher's self-research, feeling of responsibility, innovation in the lessons, making the lesson interesting and lively.

Key words: innovation, technology, efficiency, specialization, information-communication, telecommunication.

Аннотация: В данной статье написано о целесообразном использовании современных технологий в изучении и преподавании английского языка, а также самоисследовании учителя, чувстве ответственности, новаторстве на уроках, делающих урок интересным и живым.

Ключевые слова: инновации, технологии, эффективность, специализация, информационно-коммуникационные, телекоммуникационные.

The new era imposes a new task and several responsibilities on the teachers of today. With the advent of modern technology, the tradition of teaching English has changed significantly. On December 10, 2012, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov adopted the decision PQ-1875, i.e. «On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages» on December 10, 2012 . According to this decision, foreign language teachers were charged with the responsibility of introducing advanced methods of teaching using modern pedagogical and information communication technologies and preparing the growing young generation to be able to speak foreign languages freely. The decision consists of several paragraphs, and the ninth paragraph of the decision describes in detail the use of innovative technologies. According to the ninth paragraph of the decision, «The National Broadcasting Company of Uzbekistan, the State Committee for Communication, Informatization and Telecommunication Technologies, the Press and Information Agency of Uzbekistan and the National Information Agency of Uzbekistan, taking into account the interests and interests of children and youth provide the following:

Preparation and broadcasting of programs on teaching foreign languages to children and teenagers on television, including through local TV channels, scientific-popular, foreign artistic and to regularly show multiplex movies with Uzbek subtitles; Significantly increasing the access of educational institutions to international sources of education and knowledge through the «ZiyoNet» network, enriching its resource center with multimedia resources, applications for personal computers and mobile devices, as well as educational and fiction literature in English, publishing newspapers and magazines decorated with specialized pictures, organizing special columns and applications for them.

Today, the importance of learning English in Uzbekistan is much higher than before. Several English language experts are implementing new methods and ways of learning English. This will definitely increase the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages. Teaching using technology has several distinct advantages. In addition, it greatly increases the efficiency of the teaching system and, in turn, helps the language learner to keep up with the times and move forward. Technology is slowly replacing traditional teaching. Today, many new programs and shows that help to teach English are regularly broadcasted on television. It should also be noted that today new methods of using modern innovative technologies have been introduced in Uzbekistan to increase the effectiveness of teaching. For example, a student who is being taught a foreign language on the basis of multimedia had the opportunity to develop four skills and learn through interesting materials both by sight and hearing. In addition, the student can guess the meaning of some words by watching live actions and tries to understand it.

Of course, the use of modern technologies of computer, radio, CD, DVD in any foreign language lessons will further advance the educational process and allow the young generation to learn foreign languages faster. The fact that some teachers do not know how to use and use technology during English lessons makes the students somewhat bored. It is for this reason that in order not to extinguish the enthusiasm of the learner, the use of technology and at least the computer during the lesson ensures that the interest of the learner increases. After all, educational materials prepared according to the learner's age, interest, ability, mastery of the lessons will definitely be effective. On the contrary, if we teachers do not choose educational materials based on these requirements, if we broadcast video films, songs or texts containing complex words to elementary school students, or if we show them through multimedia, computers, When we present teaching materials

with very simple texts to elementary and high school students or groups, the students' interest in learning the language gradually fades and they don't master the lessons. This, in turn, can lead to a drop in grades and a loss of respect for the teacher in front of the students. So, it follows that the main task is not just to use technologies during the lesson, but to be able to use them in their place and to ensure that the use of technologies serves to increase the student's knowledge. According to the requirements of the current CEFR, i.e. International European Education Standards, the four competences of learning in English: (writing, reading, listening, speaking) are conducted. Effective and appropriate use of technologies during lessons is important. For example, listening comprehension lessons have their own rules for playing audio texts. It is important that the main goal is for the learner to understand the audio material he is listening to and be able to analyze it without difficulty. For this, the first thing is to prepare the environment for playing the audio material, in which the listeners provide a quiet environment, and the teacher focuses on the quality of the audio being played and that the sound amplifiers are working well, and the exercises to be performed before and after the audio are played. Ready and students should be provided with handouts. After all the requirements are fulfilled, the teacher can start broadcasting the audio material to the students. Listening is done at least twice, otherwise language learners may not understand the topic and may not be able to perform the exercises correctly after listening to the audio material. It is also a very effective way to show students videos, clips, and discuss them using multimedia in the process of teaching using technology in speaking and writing. It is possible to use the vocabulary familiar to the learners, to explain the words if there are new and complex words, and after completing the exercises related to the new words, it is possible to show the video material. . In order to carry out this process, it is

important to have a quiet, noise-free environment, a comfortable and clean classroom, the possibility of watching for everyone, and checking that the loudspeakers are working. Before posting the video, the students should discuss the topic of the video to be shown, conduct a question and answer session, and after making sure that the students are really interested in the topic, the video material should be posted. When the video is over, the teacher should be interested in the students' thoughts about the video and do exercises. When these stages are properly implemented, these lessons will definitely contribute to the growth of students' interests and knowledge. It follows from this that the role of modern technologies in enriching our lessons, interesting students, enriching their knowledge is incomparable. Being able to use them correctly and appropriately is the main guarantee of our success.

References:

PQ 1875 Decision «On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages». «People's Word» newspaper, page 2. December 10, 2012

Boswood, T. (1997). *New Ways of Using Computers in Language Teaching (New Ways in Tesol Series II)*, California: Teachers of English to Speakers of Other Languages.

Harmer, J. (2007). *How to teach English*, Harlow, Essex: Pearson-Longman

Johnson, D.,